

A Study on $(\lambda - \mu)$ Zweier Sequences and Their Behaviour in Neutrosophic Normed Spaces

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Abstract. Ideal convergence of sequences in neutrosophic normed spaces is defined by Ömer Kişi [12]. This paper defines new sequence spaces using the Zweier matrix and neutrosophic norm. We explore (λ, μ) -Zweier convergence, (λ, μ) ideal convergence of double sequences in neutrosophic norm. We show that a double sequence that is (λ, μ) -Zweier convergent or ideal convergent has a unique limit with respect to neutrosophic norm. Additionally, we prove that (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal convergence is equivalent to (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal Cauchy for a double sequence in neutrosophic normed space.

Keywords: Neutrosophic normed space, Statistical convergence, $(\lambda - \mu)$ Zweier convergence, I -convergence.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

The concept of fuzzy sets was introduced by Lotfi A. Zadeh [24] in 1965 as a mathematical framework to deal with uncertainty and vagueness in data. In a fuzzy set, each element is assigned a membership value ranging from 0 to 1, indicating the degree of membership of that element in the set. Kaleva, O. and Seikkala, S. (1984) [7] defined fuzzy metric space and Felbin, C. (1992) [4], Bag, T. and Samanta, S. K. (2003) [2] studied fuzzy normed linear space. Krassimir Atanassov [1] generalized the notion of fuzzy set to intuitionistic fuzzy set. Park [19] defined intuitionistic fuzzy metric space In 1995, Florentin Smarandache [23], [22] introduced the concept of neutrosophic sets as an extension of intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Neutrosophic sets aim to handle three types of indeterminacy: membership, non-membership and indeterminacy, represented by the values of truth-membership, falsehood-membership, and indeterminacy-membership respectively. Kirişci, M. and Şimşek, N. [10], [11] defined metric on neutrosophic set and also studied statistical convergence.

Concept of Statistical convergence was given H. Fast [5]. λ statistical convergence was introduced by Mursaleen [16]. λ statistical convergence is the extension of $[V, \lambda]$ summability [14]. Mursaleen et al. [17] defined the concept of (λ, μ) convergence for double sequence. The I-convergence [13] gives a unifying look on several types of convergence related to the statistical convergence. Mursaleen and Mohiuddine [18] defined I-convergence for double sequences in intuitionistic fuzzy normed spaces. In neutrosophic normed spaces, statistically convergent and statistically Cauchy double sequences are defined and studied by Granados C and Dhital [6]. Khan V. A. and Faisal M. [8], Khan V. A. and Ahmad M. [9] defined (λ, μ) Zweier ideal convergence on neutrosophic normed space and studied Cesaro summability in neutrosophic normed spaces respectively.. Zweier-Verfahren is a German word, in which Zwei means two and Verfahren means method. Zweier matrix or operator is denoted as Z^ρ , where $\rho \neq 1$. Let $x = (\xi_n) \in \omega$ where $\omega = \{x = (\xi_n) : \xi_n \in \mathbb{R}/\mathbb{C}\}$, then Z^ρ is defined as

$$Z^\rho = Z_{ik} = \begin{cases} \rho, & i = k \\ 1 - \rho, & i - 1 = k \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

Şengönül [21], define new sequence $y = (y_n)$ as Z^ρ transform of the sequence $x = (\xi_n)$,

$$y_n = Z^\rho(\xi_n) = \rho\xi_n + (1 - \rho)\xi_{n-1} \tag{2}$$

where $\xi_{-1} = 0$ and $\rho \neq 1$. Matrix

$$Z^\rho = \begin{bmatrix} \rho & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 1 - \rho & \rho & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 1 - \rho & \rho & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 1 - \rho & \rho & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ \cdot & \cdot & 0 & 1 - \rho & \rho & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ \cdot & \dots \\ \cdot & \dots \\ \cdot & \dots \end{bmatrix}.$$

Definition 1.1. [20] A double sequence $x = (\xi_{gh})$ is said to be convergent(Pringsheim’s Sense) to $\mathfrak{p} > 0$, if for every $\kappa > 0$, there exist $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$| \xi_{gh} - \mathfrak{p} | < \kappa, \text{ whenever } g, h \geq N.$$

Definition 1.2. [20] A double sequence $x = (\xi_{gh})$ is said to be Cauchy (Pringsheim’s Sense), if for every $\kappa > 0$ there exist $\mathfrak{N} \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$| \xi_{gh} - \xi_{pq} | < \kappa, \text{ whenever } g \geq p \geq \mathfrak{N} \text{ and } h \geq q \geq \mathfrak{N}.$$

Definition 1.3. Let $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$, if the sequence $\frac{|\mathcal{K}(g, h)|}{nm}$ is convergent (Pringsheim's Sense), then we say that \mathcal{K} has double natural density and defined as

$$\delta_2(\mathcal{K}) = (P) \lim_{g, h} \frac{|\mathcal{K}(g, h)|}{gh}$$

where $\mathcal{K}(g, h) = \{(p, q) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : p \leq g \text{ and } q \leq h\}$. If, $g = h$ Christopher's [3] two-dimensional natural density is obtained.

Definition 1.4. [20] A double sequence $x = (\xi_{gh})$ is said to be statistically convergent to $\mathfrak{p} > 0$, if for every $\kappa > 0$,

$$\mathcal{A} = \{(g, h) : g \leq n, h \leq m \text{ such that } |\xi_{gh} - \mathfrak{p}| \geq \kappa\}$$

has $\delta_2(\mathcal{A}) = 0$.

Definition 1.5. [20] A double sequence $x = (\xi_{gh})$ is said to be statistically Cauchy, if for every $\kappa > 0$, there exist $\mathfrak{N} = \mathfrak{N}(\kappa)$ and $\mathfrak{M} = \mathfrak{M}(\kappa)$ such that for all $g, p \geq \mathfrak{N}$ and $h, q \geq \mathfrak{M}$ the set

$$\mathcal{A} = \{(g, h) : g \leq \mathfrak{N}, h \leq \mathfrak{M} \text{ such that } |\xi_{gh} - \xi_{pq}| \geq \kappa\}$$

has $\delta_2(\mathcal{A}) = 0$.

Definition 1.6. [15] If continuous mapping $\star : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ meets the following requirements, it is called a continuous t -norm :

(a) $\star(\eta, \mathfrak{z}) = \star(\mathfrak{z}, \eta)$ and $\star(\eta, \star(\mathfrak{z}, \mathfrak{c})) = \star(\star(\eta, \mathfrak{z}), \mathfrak{c})$, for all $\eta, \mathfrak{z}, \mathfrak{c} \in [0, 1]$,

(b) $\star(\eta, 1) = \eta, \forall \eta \in [0, 1]$,

(c) $\eta \leq \mathfrak{c}$ and $\mathfrak{z} \leq \mathfrak{d} \implies \star(\eta, \mathfrak{z}) \leq \star(\mathfrak{c}, \mathfrak{d})$, for each $\eta, \mathfrak{z}, \mathfrak{c}, \mathfrak{d} \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 1.7. [15] If continuous mapping $\bullet : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ meets the following requirements, it is called continuous t -conorm if:

(a) $\bullet(\eta, \mathfrak{z}) = \bullet(\mathfrak{z}, \eta)$ and $\bullet(\eta, \bullet(\mathfrak{z}, \mathfrak{c})) = \bullet(\bullet(\eta, \mathfrak{z}), \mathfrak{c})$, for all $\eta, \mathfrak{z}, \mathfrak{c} \in [0, 1]$

(b) $\bullet(\eta, 0) = \eta, \forall \eta \in [0, 1]$,

(c) $\eta \leq \mathfrak{c}$ and $\eta \leq \mathfrak{d} \implies \bullet(\eta, \eta) \leq \bullet(\mathfrak{c}, \mathfrak{d})$ for each $\eta, \mathfrak{z}, \mathfrak{c}, \mathfrak{d} \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 1.8. [11] Let V, \star , and \bullet be linear space, continuous t -norm and continuous t -conorm respectively. A four tuple of the form $\{V, \phi(z, \cdot), \psi(z, \cdot), \gamma(z, \cdot) : z \in V\}$, is called neutrosophic normed space where ϕ, ψ , and γ are fuzzy sets on $V \times \mathbb{R}^+$ which satisfy the following conditions:

(i) $0 \leq \phi(\nu, p), \psi(\nu, p), \gamma(\nu, p) \leq 1$ for all $p \in \mathbb{R}^+$,

(ii) $0 \leq \phi(\nu, p) + \psi(\nu, p) + \gamma(\nu, p) \leq 3$ for all $p \in \mathbb{R}^+$,

(iii) $\phi(\nu, p) = 1$ (for $p > 0$) if and only if $\nu = 0$,

- (iv) $\phi(\alpha\nu, p) = \phi(\nu, \frac{p}{|\alpha|})$ for $\alpha \neq 0$
- (v) $\star(\phi(\nu, p), \phi(y, q)) \leq \phi(\nu + y, p + q)$
- (vi) $\phi(\nu, .)$ is continuous and non-decreasing
- (vii) $\lim_{p \rightarrow \infty} \phi(\nu, p) = 1,$
- (viii) $\psi(\nu, p) = 0$ for $(p > 0)$ if and only if $\nu = 0,$
- (ix) $\psi(\alpha\nu, p) = \psi(\nu, \frac{p}{|\alpha|})$ for $\alpha \neq 0,$
- (x) $\bullet(\psi(\nu, p), \psi(y, q)) \geq \psi(\nu + y, p + q)$
- (xi) $\psi(\nu, .)$ is continuous and non-increasing,
- (xii) $\lim_{p \rightarrow \infty} \psi(\nu, p) = 0,$
- (xiii) $\gamma(\nu, p) = 0$ (for $p > 0$) if and only if $\nu = 0,$
- (xiv) $\gamma(\alpha\nu, p) = \gamma(\nu, \frac{p}{|\alpha|})$ if $\alpha \neq 0,$
- (xv) $\bullet(\gamma(\nu, p), \gamma(y, q)) \geq \gamma(\nu + y, p + q),$
- (xvi) $\gamma(\nu, .)$ is continuous and non-increasing,
- (xvii) $\lim_{p \rightarrow \infty} \gamma(\nu, p) = 0,$
- (xviii) If $p \leq 0$ then $\phi(\nu, p) = 0, \psi(\nu, p) = 1,$ and $\gamma(\nu, \mathbf{p}) = 1$

Then $\mathcal{N} = (\phi, \psi, \gamma)$ is called neutrosophic norm. Throughout the paper we will use usual t -norm and usual t -conorm i.e; $\star(\tau, \varrho) = \min\{\tau, \varrho\}$ and $\bullet(\tau, \varrho) = \max\{\tau, \varrho\}.$

Example 1.9. 11 Let $(V, \|\cdot\|)$ be a normed space. Let ϕ, ψ, γ be Fuzzy sets on $V \times \mathbb{R}^+$ such that, for $t \geq \|\mathfrak{A}\|$

$$\phi(\mathfrak{A}, t) = \begin{cases} 0, & t \leq 0 \\ \frac{t}{t + \|\mathfrak{A}\|}, & t > 0, \end{cases} \quad \psi(\mathfrak{A}, t) = \begin{cases} 0, & t \leq 0 \\ \frac{\|\mathfrak{A}\|}{t + \|\mathfrak{A}\|}, & t > 0, \end{cases} \quad \text{and } \gamma(\mathfrak{A}, t) = \frac{\|\mathfrak{A}\|}{t}$$

for all $\mathfrak{A} \in V$ and $t \geq 0.$ If $t \leq \|\mathfrak{A}\|$ then $\phi(\mathfrak{A}, t) = 0, \psi(\mathfrak{A}, t) = 1$ and $\gamma(\mathfrak{A}, t) = 1.$ Then $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ is neutrosophic normed space.

Now we will discuss about the convergence of the sequence (ζ_k) in neutrosophic normed space $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet).$

Definition 1.10. [11] Let (ξ_g) be sequence in NNS $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ Then (ξ_g) is said to be convergent to $\mathbf{p} \in V$ if for each $t > 0$ and $\kappa \in (0,1)$ there exists $g_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\phi(\xi_g - \mathbf{p}, t) > 1 - \kappa, \psi(\xi_g - \mathbf{p}, t) < \kappa \text{ and } \gamma(\xi_g - \mathbf{p}, t) < \kappa \tag{3}$$

for all $g \geq g_0.$

Definition 1.11. [11] Let (ξ_g) be sequence in NNS $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ Then (ξ_g) is said to be Cauchy if, for each $t > 0$ and $\kappa \in (0,1)$ there exists $g_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\phi(\xi_k - \xi_h, t) > 1 - \kappa, \psi(\xi_k - \xi_h, t) < \kappa \text{ and } \gamma(\xi_k - \xi_h, t) < \kappa \tag{4}$$

for all $h, k \geq g_0$.

Definition 1.12. [6] Let $(V, \phi, \psi, \gamma, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS. A double sequence $x = (\xi_{gh})$ in V is said to be convergent statistically to \mathbf{p} if, for each $\kappa > 0$ and $t > 0$

$$\delta_2\{(g, h) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \phi(\xi_{gh} - \mathbf{p}, t) \leq 1 - \kappa, \psi(\xi_{gh} - \mathbf{p}, t) \geq \kappa \text{ and } \gamma(\xi_{gh} - \mathbf{p}, t) \geq \kappa\} = 0.$$

Definition 1.13. Let $\Upsilon = (\Upsilon_g)$ and $\Pi = (\Pi_h)$ be two positive non-decreasing sequences and $\lim_{g \rightarrow \infty} \Upsilon_g = \infty, \lim_{h \rightarrow \infty} \Pi_h = \infty$, defined as

$$\Upsilon_{g+1} \leq \Upsilon_g + 1, \quad \text{where } \Upsilon_1 = 0. \tag{5}$$

$$\Pi_{h+1} \leq \Pi_h + 1, \quad \text{where } \mu_1 = 0. \tag{6}$$

Let $I_g = [g - \Upsilon_g + 1, g]$ and $I_h = [h - \Pi_h + 1, h]$. Then

$$\delta_{\Upsilon, \Pi}(\mathcal{K}) = \lim_{g, h \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\Upsilon_g \Pi_h} \left| \{(i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : (i, j) \in \mathcal{K}\} \right|$$

is the (Υ, Π) density of the set $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$. If $\Upsilon_g = g$ and $\Pi_h = h$, the (Υ, Π) density reduces to natural double density of \mathcal{K} . The generalized double Valée Poussin mean is

$$t_{g, h} = \frac{1}{\Upsilon_g \Pi_h} \sum_{i \in I_g} \sum_{j \in I_h} \xi_{ij}.$$

Throughout the paper we will denote the sequences 5,6 by $\lambda = (\lambda_i)$ and $\mu = (\mu_i)$ respectively.

2. Main Results

Definition 2.1. Let $(V, \phi, \psi, \gamma, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS and I^2 be an admissible ideal in $\mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$. A double sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ in V is said to be I^2 -convergent to ξ if, for each $\epsilon > 0$ and $t > 0$ the set

$$\{(m, n) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \phi(\xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \psi(\xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon \text{ and } \gamma(\xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon\} \in I^2.$$

Definition 2.2. Let $(V, \phi, \psi, \gamma, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS. A double sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ in V is said to be (λ, μ) -Zweier convergent to ξ with respect to neutrosophic norm (ϕ, ψ, γ) if, for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $t > 0$, there exists a positive integer $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon,$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon,$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon$$

for all $m, n \geq n_0$ and write it as $(\lambda, \mu) - \lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} = \xi$.

Definition 2.3. Let $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS and I^2 is an admissible ideal. A double sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ in V is said to be (λ, μ) - Zweier ideal convergent to ξ with respect to neutrosophic norm (ϕ, ψ, γ) , if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and for all $t > 0$, the set

$$\left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon, \right. \\ \left. \text{and } \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in I^2.$$

In short we write $(\phi, \psi, \gamma) - I^2_{(\lambda, \mu)} - \lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} = \xi$

Definition 2.4. Let $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS. A double sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ in V is said to be (λ, μ) - Zweier Cauchy sequence with respect to neutrosophic norm (ϕ, ψ, γ) , if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and for all $t > 0$, there exists N such that

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \\ \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \geq \epsilon, \\ \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \geq \epsilon.$$

for all $m, n, k, p \geq N$.

Definition 2.5. Let $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS and I^2 is an admissible ideal. A double sequence $\xi = (\xi_{mn})$ in V is said to be (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal Cauchy sequence if for each $\epsilon > 0$ and $t > 0$ there exists a positive integer N such that

$$\left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \right. \\ \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \geq \epsilon, \\ \left. \text{and } \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in I^2.$$

Lemma 2.6. Let $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS and $I^2 \subseteq \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$ be an admissible ideal. Let $x = (\xi_{mn})$ be a double sequence in V , then the following are equivalent

(i) $(\phi, \psi, \gamma) - I^2_{(\lambda, \mu)} - \lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{Z}^q(\xi_{mn}) = \mathcal{L}$.

$$(ii) \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{L}, t) \leq 1 - \kappa \right\} \in I^2,$$

$$\left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{L}, t) \geq \kappa \right\} \in I^2 \text{ and}$$

$$\left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{L}, t) \geq \kappa \right\} \in I^2 \text{ for all } \kappa > 0 \text{ and } t > 0.$$

$$(iii) \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{L}, t) > 1 - \kappa \right\} \in F(I^2),$$

$$\left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{L}, t) < \kappa \right\} \in F(I^2) \text{ and}$$

$$\left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{L}, t) < \kappa \right\} \in F(I^2) \text{ for all } \kappa > 0 \text{ and } t > 0.$$

$$(iv) (\phi, \psi, \gamma) - I^2_{(\lambda, \mu)} - \lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{L}, t) = 1,$$

$$(\phi, \psi, \gamma) - I^2_{(\lambda, \mu)} - \lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{L}, t) = 0 \text{ and}$$

$$(\phi, \psi, \gamma) - I^2_{(\lambda, \mu)} - \lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{L}, t) = 0 \text{ for all } \kappa > 0 \text{ and } t > 0.$$

Theorem 2.7. Let $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS and I^2 is an admissible ideal. If a double sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ in V is (λ, μ) - Zweier ideal convergent with respect to neutrosophic norm (ϕ, ψ, γ) , then its limit is unique.

Proof. We will prove it by contradiction i.e. Let on contrary that the sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ converges to two limits (say) ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 . By definition 2.3, for a given $\epsilon > 0$, choose $\kappa > 0$ such that $(1 - \kappa) \star (1 - \kappa) > 1 - \epsilon$ and $\kappa \star \kappa < \epsilon$. Then for $t > 0$

$$A_{\phi,1}(\kappa, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_1, \frac{t}{2}\right) \leq 1 - \kappa \right\} \in I^2.$$

$$A_{\phi,2}(\kappa, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_2, \frac{t}{2}\right) \leq 1 - \kappa \right\} \in I^2.$$

$$A_{\psi,1}(\kappa, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \psi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_1, \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \kappa \right\} \in I^2.$$

$$A_{\psi,2}(\kappa, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \psi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_2, \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \kappa \right\} \in I^2.$$

$$A_{\gamma,1}(\kappa, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \gamma\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_1, \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \kappa \right\} \in I^2.$$

$$A_{\gamma,2}(\kappa, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \gamma \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_2, \frac{t}{2} \right) \geq \kappa \right\} \in I^2.$$

Now the following set

$$A_{\phi,\psi,\gamma}(\kappa, t) = [A_{\phi,1}(\kappa, t) \cup A_{\phi,2}(\kappa, t)] \cap [A_{\psi,1}(\kappa, t) \cup A_{\psi,2}(\kappa, t)] \cap [A_{\gamma,1}(\kappa, t) \cup A_{\gamma,2}(\kappa, t)] \in I^2$$

$$A_{\phi,\psi,\gamma}(\kappa, t) \in I^2 \implies A_{\phi,\psi,\gamma}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t) \in F(I^2).$$

If $(i, j) \in A_{\phi,\psi,\gamma}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t)$, then there are three cases. Either $(i, j) \in A_{\phi,1}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t) \cap A_{\phi,2}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t)$ or $(i, j) \in A_{\psi,1}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t) \cap A_{\psi,2}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t)$ or $(i, j) \in A_{\gamma,1}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t) \cap A_{\gamma,2}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t)$. Firstly, if $(i, j) \in A_{\phi,1}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t) \cap A_{\phi,2}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_1, \frac{t}{2} \right) &> 1 - \kappa \\ \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_2, \frac{t}{2} \right) &> 1 - \kappa \end{aligned}$$

Now take $(a, b) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$, such that

$$\phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{ab} - \ell_1, \frac{t}{2} \right) > \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_1, \frac{t}{2} \right) > 1 - \kappa$$

and

$$\phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{ab} - \ell_2, \frac{t}{2} \right) > \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_2, \frac{t}{2} \right) > 1 - \kappa.$$

Select (a, b) for (m, n) such that the maximum hold i.e. $\max \left\{ \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_1, \frac{t}{2} \right), \psi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_2, \frac{t}{2} \right), \gamma \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \ell_2, \frac{t}{2} \right) : m \in \Lambda_i, n \in \Lambda_j \right\}$. Then, we have

$$\phi(\ell_1 - \ell_2, t) \geq \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{ab} - \ell_1, \frac{t}{2} \right) \star \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{ab} - \ell_2, \frac{t}{2} \right) > (1 - \kappa) \star (1 - \kappa) > 1 - \epsilon$$

Since $\epsilon > 0$ was arbitrary, for every $t > 0$, we get $\phi(\ell_1 - \ell_2, t) = 1$, that means $\ell_1 = \ell_2$. For other cases if, $(i, j) \in A_{\psi,1}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t) \cap A_{\psi,2}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t)$ or $(i, j) \in A_{\gamma,1}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t) \cap A_{\gamma,2}^{\mathbb{C}}(\kappa, t)$, in similar fashion we get $\psi(\ell_1 - \ell_2, t) > \epsilon$ and $\gamma(\ell_1 - \ell_2, t) > \epsilon$ for $t > 0$. Hence for each case, we get $\ell_1 = \ell_2$. Hence limit is unique. \square

Theorem 2.8. *Let $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS. If a double sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ in V is (λ, μ) -Zweier convergent with respect to neutrosophic norm (ϕ, ψ, γ) , then its limit is unique.*

Proof. Let $(\lambda, \mu) - \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} = \xi_1$ and $(\lambda, \mu) - \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} = \xi_2$. Given $\epsilon > 0$, select $\kappa > 0$ such that $(1 - \kappa) \star (1 - \kappa) > 1 - \epsilon$ and $\kappa \bullet \kappa < \epsilon$. Then for any $t > 0$, there exists $n_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_1, t) > 1 - \epsilon$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_1, t) < \epsilon$$

and

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_1, t) < \epsilon$$

for all $i, j \geq n_1$. There also exists n_2 such that

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_2, t) > 1 - \epsilon$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_2, t) < 1 - \epsilon$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \lambda(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_2, t) < \epsilon$$

for all $i, j \geq n_2$. Now chose $n_0 = \max\{n_1, n_2\}$. Then for all $n \geq n_0$, we have $(a, b) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{ab} - \xi_1, t) > \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_1, t) > 1 - \kappa$$

. and

$$\phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{ab} - \xi_2, t) > \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_2, t) > 1 - \kappa.$$

Hence, we get

$$\phi(\xi_1 - \xi_2, t) \geq \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_1, t) \star \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi_2, t) > (1 - \kappa) \star (1 - \kappa) > 1 - \epsilon.$$

Since ϵ was arbitrary. Hence we get $\phi(\xi_1 - \xi_2, t) = 1$ for all $t > 0$. Hence $\xi_1 = \xi_2$. Similarly, we will prove for ψ and γ that $\psi(\xi_1 - \xi_2, t) < \epsilon$ and $\gamma(\xi_1 - \xi_2, t) < \epsilon$ for any $\epsilon > 0$. Hence we get $\psi(\xi_1 - \xi_2, t) = 0$ and $\gamma(\xi_1 - \xi_2, t) = 0$ for $t > 0$, this implies that $\xi_1 = \xi_2$. \square

Theorem 2.9. Let $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS. (λ, μ) -Zweier convergence of a double sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ in V implies (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal convergence of $x = (\xi_{mn})$ with respect to neutrosophic norm and $(\lambda, \mu) - \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} = (\phi, \psi, \gamma) - I_{(\lambda, \mu)}^2 - \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} = \xi$.

Proof. Let sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ is (λ, μ) -Zweier convergent to ξ . Then for $\epsilon > 0$ and $t > 0$, there exists positive integer N such that

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) > 1 - \epsilon,$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) < \epsilon,$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) < \epsilon$$

for all $i, j \geq N$. Then the set

$$R(\epsilon, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon, \text{ and } \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon, \right\}.$$

is contained in the set $Q = \{(1, 1), (1, 2), (2, 1), (2, 2), \dots, (N - 1, N - 1)\}$. Since I^2 is an admissible ideal. We get, $R(\epsilon, t) \subseteq Q \in I^2$. Hence (λ, μ) -Zweier convergence of a double sequence implies (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal convergence and $(\phi, \psi, \gamma) - I^2_{(\lambda, \mu)} - \lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} = \xi$. \square

Theorem 2.10. *Let $(V, \mathcal{N}, \star, \bullet)$ be a NNS. A double sequence $x = (\xi_{mn})$ in V is (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal convergent if and only if it is (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal Cauchy.*

Proof. Let $x = (\xi_{mn})$ in V is (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal Cauchy sequence but not (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal convergent in V with respect to neutrosophic norm (ϕ, ψ, γ) . Now, by the definition of (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal Cauchy for each $\epsilon > 0$ and $t > 0$, there exists positive integer N such that

$$G(\epsilon, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \right. \\ \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \geq \epsilon, \\ \left. \text{and } \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in I^2.$$

and

$$H(\epsilon, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{2}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \right. \\ \left. \frac{2}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \psi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \epsilon, \text{ and} \right. \\ \left. \frac{2}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \gamma\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in F(I^2)$$

Since

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \geq \frac{2}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) > 1 - \epsilon,$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \leq \frac{2}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \psi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) < \epsilon,$$

and

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \leq \frac{2}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \gamma\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) < \epsilon.$$

If

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) > \frac{1 - \epsilon}{2}, \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \psi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) < \frac{\epsilon}{2},$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \gamma\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) < \frac{\epsilon}{2}.$$

Then, we have

$$\delta(\lambda, \mu) \left(\left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \right. \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \geq \epsilon, \right. \\ \left. \left. \text{and } \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right) = 0$$

That is $G(\epsilon, t) \in F(I^2)$, which is a contradiction. Hence, sequence $\xi = (\xi_{mn})$ is (λ, μ) -Zweier ideal convergent with respect to neutrosophic norm.

Conversely, suppose that $(\phi, \psi, \gamma) - I^2_{(\lambda, \mu)} - \lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} = \xi$. Choose $r > 0$, such that $(1 - r) \star (1 - r) > 1 - \epsilon$ and $r \bullet r < \epsilon$. For $t > 0$ define

$$W(r, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2} \right) \leq 1 - r, \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \psi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2} \right) \geq r, \text{ and} \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n \in \Lambda_j} \gamma \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2} \right) \geq r \right\} \in I^2$$

or $W(r, t)^c \in F(I^2)$. Assume $(k, p) \in W(r, t)^c$. Then, we get

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{p \in \Lambda_j} \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2} \right) > 1 - r \\ \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{p \in \Lambda_j} \psi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2} \right) < r \\ \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \xi, \frac{t}{2} \right) < r$$

For every $\epsilon > 0$, we take

$$U(\epsilon, t) = \left\{ (i, j) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t \right) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t \right) \geq \epsilon, \right. \\ \left. \text{and } \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{m, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{n, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{mn} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t \right) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in I^2.$$

Now we will show that $U(\epsilon, t) \subset W(r, t)$. Let $(u, v) \in U(\epsilon, t)$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t \right) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \\ \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t \right) \geq \epsilon, \\ \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t \right) \geq \epsilon.$$

Here we are going to divide it into three cases as follows

Case1 :

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi \left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t \right) \leq 1 - \epsilon.$$

Then

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) \leq 1 - r \implies (u, v) \in W(r, t).$$

Otherwise, if $\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) > 1 - r$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \epsilon &\geq \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t\right) \\ &\geq \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) \star \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{p \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) \\ &> (1 - r) \star (1 - r) \\ &> 1 - \epsilon. \end{aligned}$$

We reach at a contradiction. Hence $U(\epsilon, t) \subset W(r, t)$.

Case2 : Consider

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v, p \in \Lambda_j} \psi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t\right) \geq \epsilon.$$

We get

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v \in \Lambda_j} \psi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq r \implies (u, v) \in W(r, t).$$

Otherwise, if

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v \in \Lambda_j} \psi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) < r.$$

Then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \epsilon &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v, p \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t\right) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) \bullet \frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{p \in \Lambda_j} \phi\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp} - \xi, \frac{t}{2}\right) \\ &< (1 - r) \bullet (1 - r) \\ &< 1 - \epsilon. \end{aligned}$$

Which is a contradiction. Hence, $U(\epsilon, t) \subset W(r, t)$.

Case 3 is similar to the case 2 , in this case we will consider that

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i \mu_j} \sum_{u, k \in \Lambda_i} \sum_{v, p \in \Lambda_j} \gamma\left(\mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{uv} - \mathcal{Z}^q \xi_{kp}, t\right) \geq \epsilon.$$

And we obtain that, $U(\epsilon, t) \subset W(r, t)$.

In each case we obtain that $U(\epsilon, t) \subset W(r, t)$. This implies that $U(\epsilon, t) \in I^2$. Hence double sequence is a Zweier ideal Cauchy sequence with respect to th neutrosophic norm (ϕ, ψ, γ) . □

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